

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Alternative solid particles selection, characterization and evaluation to be implemented as thermal energy storage material and heat transfer fluid in concentrating solar power from a circular economy perspective.
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	THERSOLPA
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Birmingham Centre for Energy Storage (BCES)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	CSP, TES, Solar power, renewable energy, circular economy
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	30/04/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	30/07/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	02/05/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	28/07/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	31
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Bank holiday, weekend
Number of days using the RI	62
Number of users granted access (group size)	
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The main focus of the project is to obtain a reduction of the electricity production costs of concentrating solar power plants with a revalorization of alternative ceramic materials. To accomplish that, a series of tasks will be completed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A selection of various alternative materials based on their global annual production. This will encompass different sectors including steelmaking and mining companies. 	

- A complete characterization of the physical, chemical and thermal properties of these materials. Thermal stability, specific heat capacity, physical and chemical stability over thermal stress cycles are the main properties to consider.

Considering this, the main objectives of this work are:

- Utilizing solid particle materials as thermal energy storage media and heat transfer fluid with a direct or indirect system of heat exchange.
- Reducing the use of molten salts solely as heat transfer fluid while maintaining solid particles as thermal energy storage media.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

In the BCES group I conducted a complete high-temperature characterization and thermal stability evaluation of various alternative ceramic materials intended for high-temperature thermal storage applications.

The initial steps with the samples involved drying and preparing them for all characterization techniques. The samples tested were:

- Silica sand
- Volcanic rock
- Demolition waste
- Mining waste (low-grade MgCO₃)
- Steel slag (black slag)
- Ladle furnace slag (ladle slag)
- Commercial sintered ceramic (ID40)

Small cylindrical tablets (1.2x5mm) and larger ones (3x12.7mm) were created for evaluation purposes using a metallic mould and an automatic press. With all the samples prepared, the following equipment was used to perform evaluation tests:

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

The scientific development will be organized in 2 steps.

- 1- Characterization and testing before thermal cycling
- 2- Characterization and testing after thermal cycling

The first step consisted of a physical characterization in SEM equipment and sample preparation after drying and grinding the particles.

The first results came from STA analysis where thermal stability and specific heat capacity of the materials were tested. In this STA analysis, a thermogravimetric (TG) evaluation was conducted to evaluate the mass loss and thermal stability in the first and second exposition at high temperature. The outcomes are as follows:

TG evaluation of:

- Silica sand; the first TG evaluation gave a total mass loss of 0.05 % in silica sand sample over the temperature range from 50 °C to 750 °C. The following tests showed no significant change in the material.
- Volcanic rock; in the TG evaluation of volcanic rock can be detected a mass gain of 0.57% in the range between 550 °C to 600 °C. This was followed by a colour change from black to red. The following tests showed no significant change in the mass.

- Demolition waste; experienced a severe mass loss of 20% from 300 °C to 600 °C. It is known that demolitions wastes could contain an important amount of Portland cement that cannot withstand high temperatures.
- Mining waste; this waste is mainly composed by MgO/MgCO₃ and CaCO₃ and it experienced a decarbonization process of MgCO₃ between 300 °C and 500 °C. The mass loss was around 5% but it remained stable over next further tests.
- Steel slag; is a by-product from steel industry and can contain many iron oxides and calcium oxides. Although in the first thermal exposure a mass loss around 4% was detected from 300 °C to 500 °C, it remained stable over next thermal tests.
- Ladle furnace slag; a huge content of MgO/MgCO₃ is also present in this material, but with a higher content in iron oxides. The outcomes of the TG evaluation were similar to the steel slag.
- Commercial sintered ceramic; this material is a sintered bauxite aimed for high pressure applications which is thermal and chemical inert. Although is not a waste or a natural material and the cost is much higher, can be a good candidate for this high temperature applications.

The specific heat capacities of all samples were calculated with the same equipment giving a range between 0.90 J/g·K and 1.15 J/g·K.

CTE and percentage of change of the materials were tested with a thermomechanical analyser (TMA). Since all materials are ceramics and have a similar composition, the CTE was similar with a variation in the same range of 10-6/°C. The steel slag and ladle furnace slag have a similar CTE from 275 °C to 500 °C of 10.26 °C⁻¹ and 9.84 °C⁻¹ respectively. The mining waste and the volcanic rock, also have a similar CTE in the same range of 16.80 °C⁻¹ and 12.59 °C⁻¹ respectively. Silica sand gave the most different outcome with near 0.40% of change between 570 °C and 590 °C caused by a solid-solid phase change. CTE in the range from 275 °C to 500 °C was 6.16 °C⁻¹. ID40, the commercial sintered ceramic, was not tested due to the complications of the pebble shape. The datasheet of the commercial material mentions a CTE of 2.75 °C⁻¹. On the other hand, demolition waste was discarded at this point as a high temperature thermal energy storage material since its huge thermal decomposition from 300 °C.

Thermal conductivity of the solids was calculated using the laser flash (LFA) equipment, the conductivity obtained of all materials varies from 0.33 W/m·K to 0.77 W/m·K at 300 °C. It is observed an increase of conductivity with temperature in all samples.

SEM imaging was useful to validate the shape and surface of the samples:

Steel slag and ladle furnace slag present an irregular shape with a circular but rough surface and a huge presence of fines. Mining waste present an average size smaller than others with a smooth surface but irregular shape. Also, volcanic rock exhibits a smooth surface and circular particles with crater-like notches. All natural and waste materials contain a large quantity of fine particles and have an irregular size distribution. On the other hand, commercial ceramics have an almost perfect circular shape with a smooth surface, and the particle size range is much more normalized.

XRD evaluation was completed before and after the thermal cycling test. This test was conducted with the most promising materials after the first thermal and physical characterization. The materials were: Volcanic rock, steel slag, silica sand and mining waste. Thanks to the XRD evaluation some chemical changes could be detected and identified.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

Thanks to the STA and LFA equipment, a thermal evaluation could be completed. Silica sand, volcanic rock, mining waste, steel slag, ladle furnace slag and the commercial ceramic showed a

good thermal stability in the range of 50 °C to 750 °C. Some of them experienced a mass change but remained stable over next cycles. A pre-treatment of natural or waste materials is important in order to stabilize the solids and ensure their thermal inertness. Specific heat capacities of all ceramic materials were similar with a slight change after the first thermal exposure in some of them. The values range between 0.90 J/g·K and 1.15 J/g·K, a fair value for a material in a thermal energy storage system. Thermal conductivity was calculated thanks to the diffusivity values obtained with the LFA equipment and with a relation between specific heat capacity, density and thermal diffusivity, thermal conductivity could be calculated.

At this point and due to its thermal stability, demolition waste was discarded from the evaluation. The significant mass loss caused by the thermal degradation of cement makes it unsuitable for applications at very high temperatures.

Silica sand present a very high stability in the whole temperature range, however, around 570 °C a solid-solid phase transition occurs that increases in around 0.40% in volume the sample. This reversible reaction detected with a TMA, could affect the packing and settlement of the particles in a storage tank leading into pressure drop of any heat transfer fluid moving through the particle bed. All other materials showed a CTE in the same range. This was calculated with a TMA equipment with a linear and volumetric expansion probe.

SEM images were crucial to verify the stability of the particles after 1000 thermal cycles completed. A start of sintering between smaller particles were observed in samples such as volcanic rock and steel slag. Also, some cracks appeared in volcanic rock and the mining waste.

XRD comparison were only conducted with the best candidates that completed the 1000 thermal cycling test: Volcanic rock, silica sand, steel slag and mining waste. With this comparison chemical changes in volcanic rock could be detected. An oxidation of metallic oxides around 580 °C started. Steel slag and mining waste also experienced some chemical changes. Silica sand remained chemically stable all over the test.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The TNA work achieved significant milestones in the complete characterization of alternative materials for thermal energy storage applications. Key findings for each material tested are summarized as follows:

- Silica sand: Exhibited good thermal and chemical stability, moderate thermal properties, and density. However, its phase change at 570 °C could pose challenges in closed systems.
 - Volcanic rock: Showed oxidation of metallic oxides present, but exhibited excellent thermal and chemical stability after this process. Its thermal properties and density were fair. Sintering of small aggregates and cracks were observed after thermal cycling.
 - Demolition waste: Not suitable for high temperatures, but could be considered for thermal energy storage at lower temperatures.
 - Mining waste: After pre-treatment and sieving, it displayed good stability and thermal properties, with a high content of MgO.
 - Steel slag: After pre-treatment and sieving, it demonstrated remarkable thermal stability. Further high-temperature pre-treatment could enhance its chemical inertness.
 - Ladle furnace slag: Similar to mining waste (>70% MgO) and thermally inert, but higher metallic oxide content may cause chemical changes at higher temperatures.
 - Commercial sintered ceramic: Showed perfect thermal and chemical stability, with high thermal properties. However, its costlier manufacturing process may impact overall competitiveness.
- Silica sand, mining waste, volcanic ash, and steel slag/ladle furnace slag showed the most promising outcomes.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)
<p>Very slow and tedious procedures for accessing the lab and equipment. The risk assignment regarding the materials that I submitted 2 months before starting my stay was not evaluated until my first day at the RI. With all the necessary changes that the document needed, the approval was delayed for almost 1 month.</p> <p>Besides this, the training and access to all the necessary equipment were carried out satisfactorily.</p>
Intended publications
<p>The outcomes of the project will be part of a thesis and also published in a scientific journal: Solar energy materials and solar cells. Part of the characterisation was started at university of Barcelona and the publication will include both results. A related work was already published in Solar RRL in 2021.</p>
Data management
<p>All data obtained during the project will be used in scientific publications, conferences and the scientific publications will be related with a thesis writing.</p>
Conclusions / additional comments
<p>Thanks to the comprehensive high-temperature characterization carried out, it has been confirmed that various low-cost alternative materials, such as volcanic ash, mining waste, and steel slags, have the capacity to serve as energy storage media over a wide range of temperatures. These materials exhibited stable behaviour both within the temperature range and after undergoing thermal stress. While a pre-treatment will be necessary, these materials demonstrated chemically and thermally inert behaviour.</p> <p>Silica sand also showed significant stability and behaviour, but it is essential to consider its phase change around 570 °C and the volume change during this process when configuring the storage tank.</p> <p>However, demolition waste was discarded due to its poor performance at high temperatures, attributed to the degradation of Portland cement present in the waste.</p> <p>The outcomes of this research will pave the way for more affordable thermal energy storage systems suitable for various applications, such as waste heat recovery, solar, or wind storage units. Additionally, it has the potential to reduce capital and operational costs in the new generation of concentrating solar power plants with thermal energy storage configuration.</p>
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
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Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
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Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>											

Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>											
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
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Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20%;">1 (excellent)</td> <td style="width: 20%;">2</td> <td style="width: 20%;">3 (neutral)</td> <td style="width: 20%;">4</td> <td style="width: 20%;">5 (poor)</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.